

Timo Korhonen, Academy of Finland/University of Helsinki

A linguist's viewpoint: formulaic language as a challenge for historical linguistics

This paper sketches a synthesis of the viewpoints that should be addressed when formulaic historical documents are subjected to linguistic study. The framework of the discussion is that of diachronic corpus linguistics and the data early medieval Latin private charters. The observations are expected to be scalable, *mutatis mutandis*, to many other formulaic premodern documents.

Scholars agree that charter formulae complicate linguistic analysis, but why exactly and to what extent remains an open question. To understand what kind of linguistic phenomena one can meaningfully study in charters, I seek to 1) clarify what formulae are from a linguistic viewpoint, 2) examine the cognitive bases of how formulae were reproduced and its implications to linguistic analysis, and 3) discuss how quantitative/computational research settings might tackle the peculiarities of charter data.

0. Data

Private charters are contracts between private persons or between a private person and local institutions. They mostly deal with selling, donating, or leasing out landed property and were written by scribes on parchment. Surviving in tens of thousands from early medieval Europe, private charters are important for historical Latin (and Romance) linguistics because they are written in a non-standard Latin that reflects developments of the spoken language. Most early medieval scribes of the formerly Latin-speaking Europe only had a limited literary education. Early medieval Latin had developed far from ancient Latin, and its spoken varieties were no doubt practically equivalent to Romance vernaculars, which, however, only got their first stable written representations later in the Middle Ages.

However, early medieval private charters cannot be used for linguistic study like balanced ready-made modern-language corpora. First, charters are formulaic. Second, they are short. Such a combination makes quantitative corpus-linguistics challenging: as any corpus of charters is necessarily highly repetitive, the normal assumptions about distributions do not apply. Moreover, language-external changes in document production radically affect distributions, as new formulae were introduced and old ones fell out.

The argumentation of this paper is mainly based on the 1,040 charters of the first two parts of the *Late Latin Charter Treebank* (LLCT1–2), a lemmatized and morphologically and syntactically annotated corpus of 1,040 private charters from the 8th/9th centuries written in Tuscany, mostly corresponding to modern-day Tuscany (483,752 tokens; AD 714–897) (Korkiakangas 2021, Korkiakangas 2020a, Korkiakangas 2020b).

There is a huge difference in repetitiveness between LLCT and “normal” Latin corpora of literary texts. Variation in corpora can be measured using metrics, such as Type/token ratio (TTR), which divides the total number of different items (types) by the total number of all items (tokens) in a text. The higher the TTR value is, the higher is the variation in the corpus. I compared the lemma-based TTR of LLCT1–2 to that of the LASLA (Laboratoire d’Analyse Statistique des Langues Anciennes) corpus of Classical Latin prose and poetry (1.8 M words, Moretti 2023) within chunks of the same size. While LASLA contains 11,234 different lemmas, LLCT1–2 only has 5,819. The same lemmas also occur much more often in LLCT, resulting into a TTR (0.014) half the size of that in LASLA (0.027). Thus, LLCT is lexically poor compared to LASLA.

1. What are charter formulae?

1.1. In previous linguistic research

In 1965, the Italian linguist Francesco Sabatini made a systematic division between what he called charters’ “parts of formulary” and their “free” parts (*parti del formulario* and *parti libere*). According to him, freely composed text is mainly found in the dispositive parts of charters, where the case-specific contents are reported, and where, consequently, the influence of the spoken language was heavy. The formulaic parts, instead, reproduced centuries-old legal Latin, which the scribes did not necessarily understand, hence the often bizarre linguistic errors and misunderstandings in them. However, even the most freely composed descriptions of the objects of transaction contain stock phrases, whereas the most crystallized dating formulae necessarily have blanks for names, numbers, and calendar terms.

Larson (2000) has discussed the theme more recently, and Sornicola (2017, 17) has expressed justified doubts about the dichotomous Sabatinian distinction. On the whole, the distinction has been adopted by much subsequent research on Latin charters, e.g., Faraoni 2018 and Korkiakangas (2016, 2018, 2021, 2023b). Korkiakangas has encoded manually each LLCT sentence either as free or formulaic in order to enable rough

statistical comparisons. Such encoding is obviously imprecise, but it has proven useful in corpus-linguistic analysis.

1.2. Repetitiveness vs. formulaicity

Formulae can be approximated in terms of repetitive sequences using n-grams, which are also ideal for visualization.

Latin is a highly inflectional language with a relatively free word order. This is why any advanced linguistic study on Latin requires a corpus that is comprehensively annotated linguistically. Moreover, the Latin of early medieval charters, especially its spelling, is often non-standard. Therefore, all distributions calculated on the plain-text word forms are bound to be misleading. LLCT is lemmatized, i.e., each word form is annotated with its dictionary form, lemma, so the n-grams can be based on lemmas.

I turned LLCT1–2 into **lemma-trigrams**, i.e., sequences of three consecutive lemmas. After that, I counted how many times each lemma-trigram occurs within LLCT and ranked them in six repetitiveness classes, which I encoded with different hues of red colour for visualization. In this way, the entire LLCT can be viewed to find out how repetitive textual matter each charter or each section of a charter contains. The repetitiveness scores demonstrate that the uniformity of document production in Tuscia increases notably under the time span examined (Figure 1). A corresponding standardization and harmonization has been detected in other areas of document writing, i.e., handwriting and spelling variation, especially in the 9th century (Korkiakangas 2023b).

Figure 1. Average repetitiveness score in LLCT1–2 by decade.

This standardization also involves the use of linguistic constructions. Figure 2 presents the diachronic change of the TTR value of inflectional genitive and the competing prepositional phrase with *de* defined on the lemma of the head word of the construction. The values are

calculated across four chronologically consecutive chunks of the corpus that contain an equal number of occurrences. The trend is decreasing with both the features, which is contrary to the expectations, given that *de* + NP is known to have replaced the inflectional genitive in the spoken language by the time of early Romance varieties. One would have expected that the TTR trend of an emergent, increasingly productive construction like *de* + NP would rather be rising, but the general impoverishment of the language of charters in the 9th century seems to have impoverished the lexical templates of all linguistic constructions, whether they were emergent, stable, or recessive. The same applies to most other linguistic features that I have analysed in LLCT. It can be concluded that, if used at face value, these metrics of lexical richness/productivity measure the standardization of charter production in LLCT. However, it might be possible to uncover real diachronic change in at least some linguistic features were the effect of corpus-internal formula standardization cleared away by carefully comparing the chronological TTR and Baayen's P (Baayen 2009) profiles of different linguistic features.¹

Figure 2. Change in lexical richness (TTR) of inflectional genitive and prepositional phrase with *de* in LLCT1–2.

Thus, early medieval charters had almost become forms with a limited number of blanks to be filled in. However, even though a late-9th-century charter may consist of almost completely repetitive sequences, it does not mean that the sequences are formulaic. For example, a trigram that occurs tens or hundreds of times may contain a certain bishop's name or be part of the description of the object of transaction, such as a farmhouse with all its belongings. Such sequences are not fully formulaic because once a bishop died, another was elected, and he could have leased out something else than a farmhouse. It

¹ Perhaps, the initially higher TTR values of *de* + NP testify to its emergent status compared to the genitive. The genitive/*de* + NP data derive from Valentini and Korhonen (2017).

just happens to be so that one bishop issued hundreds of charters and many of them happened to be lease contracts of farmhouses. Consequently, human scholarly judgement is needed to distinguish between the formulae proper and the blanks that can be filled in with words that tend to occur multiple times.

I showed in Korkiakangas (2022) that two maximally similar lease contracts, *ChLA* 79.34 and *ChLA* 79.39, both written by the scribe Adalfridi in Lucca in 848, differ from each other as highlighted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Case-specific matter in *ChLA* 79.34 and *ChLA* 79.39.

Manifestu/-a/-i sum/-us ego/nos NAME, TITLE, PATRONYM quia tu/vos NAME, TITLE, PATRONYM per cartula livellario ordine firmasti/-s me/nos in OBJECT OF TRANSFER in TOPONYM1, TOPONYM2, ETC.; THE OBJECT OF TRANSFER vero ipsa/-e/-is una cum terris, vineis, cultum vel incultum, omnia res/quantum ad ipsa/-e/-is OBJECT OF TRANSFER est pertenentes, me/nos firmasti/-s in integrum ...¹; tali vero ordine, ut ego/nos et heredes meis/nostri/-s in suprascripta/-o/-is/ipsa/-o/-is OBJECT OF TRANSFER residere et habitare debeamus et tam ipsa/-o/-is OBJECT OF TRANSFER quam et predicta/-o/-is OBJECT OF TRANSFER quas mihi/nobis dedisti/-s bene laborare et gubernare seo in omnibus meliorare debeam/-us.

The words capitalised in red highlight the changing, non-formulaic, case-specific information that differed from one legal transaction to another, such as names, titles, and the property transferred. The red minuscule text stands for the words or inflections that belong to the formula but change in response to case-specific information or grammatical agreement. The black text marks textual matter that is not case-specific but common to all representatives of this type of lease contract and, consequently, can be claimed formulaic. However, even the black text differs between the two charters. The illustration of Figure 4 leaves out the non-formulaic information and highlights those words that are attested to in only one of the two charters: yellow for those present exclusively in *ChLA* 79.34 and blue for those present exclusively in *ChLA* 79.39 (Korkiakangas 2022, 12–13).

Figure 4. Variation of formulae in *ChLA* 79.34 and *ChLA* 79.39.

Manifestu sum ego ... quia tu ... per cartula livellario ordine firmasti me in casa et res illa in ...; casa vero ipsa una cum terris, vineis, cultum vel incultum, omnia res/quantum ad ipsa casa est pertenentes, me firmasti in integrum ...; tali vero ordine, ut ego et heredes meis in suprascripta/ipsa casa residere et habitare debeamus et tam ipsa casa quam et predicta res quas mihi dedisti bene laborare et gubernare seo in omnibus meliorare debeamus.

² An exception clause *exceptato ... dedisti* in *ChLA* 79.34 is bypassed at (...) to keep the comparison concise.

The genuinely formulaic matter is in minority. On average, formulae are disrupted every three words by case-specific information or by variations in the formula itself. These observations elicit the question how to identify (and visualize) formulae within an entire charter corpus. An answer is to combine supervised and unsupervised approaches.

1.3. Formulae as diplomatic text re-use

The previous examples suggested that it is not far-fetched to conceptualize early medieval charters as realizations of text re-use templates. I examined the variation of the formulae of the so-called *constat* and *manifestus sum* clauses, which open the dispositive part of various document types in early medieval Tuscia in Korkiakangas (2023a). I used trigrams to detect the most frequent lemmas and lemma collocates co-occurring with the lemmas *consto* and *manifestus*. The approach involved a supervised element based on my linguistic knowledge: I excluded lemmas with less than three (with *consto*) or ten (with *manifestus*) occurrences and selected a set of 32 lemmas/lemma collocates co-occurring with the lemma *consto* and a set of 39 lemmas/lemma collocates co-occurring with the lemma *manifestus* that were linguistically meaningful (Korkiakangas 2023a: 12). Finally, I ran a cluster analysis and ended up with what I called formula templates.

The template in Figure 5 presents the variation in what appears to be an older (late-8th-century) Tuscan variant for sales contracts: the bars show which elements the formula may include and how common each element is within the corpus. The boxes and connector lines link elements that are semantically equal or otherwise mutually replaceable. Figure 6 shows a later (9th-century) variant of the functionally same formula. It testifies to a notable standardization, along which the formulae also became more compact.

Figure 5. Older Tuscan sales contract *constat* template (Korkiakangas 2023a: 20–22)

Figure 6. Later Luccan sales contract *constat* template (Korkiakangas 2023a: 22–24)

While ideal for visualization, formula templates can also help detect instances of previously defined formulae within new datasets. This can be done using skip-grams instead of linear n-grams. The advantage of the template method is that it reduces the multidimensional reality into a feasible number of human-readable simplifications that can be then mapped with diachronic and diatopic factors.

2. The cognitive bases: language, formula reproduction, and historical context

This section demonstrates that not all linguistic features of early medieval charters can be equally well subjected to linguistic analysis because the linkage between single grammatical features of charter texts and the changing linguistic reality varies. Such a demonstration first calls for an examination of the cognitive bases of how formulae were reproduced when a scribe compiled a charter.

2.1. *Reproduction mechanisms of charter formulae*

As stated above, early medieval private charters are relatively short and simple by structure. There is much evidence that early medieval scribes reproduced the formulae from memory, not from formulary books or model charter collections, as was customary later in the Middle Ages and with more complex documents, such as imperial or papal diplomas. I discuss this theme at length in Korkiakangas (2022).

First, a constant recourse to a model would severely disturb the writing process, as the continuous formula sequences were very short, as was seen in section 1.2. Second, no formulary books survive from early medieval Italy, and even the famous formularies of Gaul, such as the *Formulae Marculfi* or *Formulae Andecavenses* are more like idea banks. Rio (2009) maintains that formularies were only economic with rare document typologies that were infrequent enough not to be memorized. Third, early medieval charters show no errors derived from direct copying, such as *saut du même au même*. Such errors abound

in manuscripts, which copyists sought to copy verbatim.

Finally, the human brain is optimal for storing semantic information as concepts, not as words, let alone words organized in a specific syntactic order. Therefore, the realizations of the same formula may vary, even when they are reproduced from memory. On the other hand, also when one is copying word by word from a model, unconscious interferences in subvocalization, i.e., the internal speech that accompanies reading and writing processes, sometimes result in copies that deviate notably from their exemplars and display L1-based interference (Korkiakangas [in press], Dain 1964). So, copying either from memory or model may involve transfer from one's native idiom, and this is what I will discuss in the following section. However, precisely because the human memory is suboptimal in recalling the specific order of items or longer chunks, such as formulae, I assume that early medieval scribes, to some extent, relied on existing charters to check the order of formula elements.

2.2. L1 transfer and formulaicity

The scribes were native speakers of a Romance-type variety that differed considerably from Classical Latin standard, the basis of many age-old legal formulae. Thus, in practice, the scribes had to learn those Latin features as L2 that were no longer present in their Romance variety. Some scholars maintain that beginning from the early 9th century, Tuscan, especially Luccan, scribes were no longer educated in the episcopal school with clerics as they had probably been in the 8th century; instead, they were now trained as apprentices in scribal *botteghe*, so they did not necessarily learn much Latin grammar, but only how to compile charter texts (Meyer 2001). This fostered a closer adherence to formulae and a general standardization of document production. This standardization did not automatically mean improvement in grammaticality, given that the formulae, which were now observed more tightly, also contained typical features of late Latin.

Nevertheless, some aspects of the scribes' grammatical performance improved in the course of the 9th century, as will be seen below, whether it was because of the scribes' improving Latin skills or certain formulae being reformed by the authorities.

Korkiakangas (2018) reveals a complex interplay between formulaicity and early medieval scribes' linguistic performance within different domains of Latin grammar. I examined ten linguistic features that are known to have changed from Classical to late Latin to find out whether they behave differently in the formulaic and non-formulaic parts of charters in LLCT1 (Figure 7). The statistical significance is the *p* value of chi-square test.

Figure 7. Ten linguistic features in formulaic and free parts of LLCT1 (based on Korciakangas 2018: 138).

	Statistically significant sensitivity to formulaicity		N	% of total of words		% distribution		Significance level
	Domain	Measured variant		Formulaic	Free	Formulaic	Free	
More salient	lexicon	81 innovative lemmas	767	1.5	9.1	-	-	p < 0.001
	morphology	future perfect form	2,315	12.3	3.5	-	-	p < 0.001
		dative plural form	154	0.8	0.4	-	-	p = 0.004
	morphology/syntax	adnominal genitive form	8,027	37.2	30.6	90.3	69.2	p < 0.001
		adnominal <i>de</i> PP	1,441	4.0	13.6	9.7	30.8	
	syntax	ACI	982	5.6	1.8	84.7	57.8	p < 0.001
conjunction clauses		235	0.9	1.3	15.3	42.2		
absolute constructions		916	4.9	1.5	-	-	p < 0.001	
	Statistically non-significant sensitivity to formulaicity		N	% of total of words		% distribution		Significance level
	Domain	Measured variant		Formulaic	Free	Formulaic	Free	
Less salient	morphology	2nd person singular -s	248	1.0	1.4	89.0	87.6	non-sign.
		2nd person singular not -s	32	0.1	0.2	11.0	12.4	
		dative singular form	3,878	15.8	21.4	-	-	
	syntax	nominative subjects	278	1.2	1.3	74.8	65.8	non-sign.
		accusative subjects	107	0.4	0.7	25.2	34.2	
		OV order	1,118	3.8	8.5	66.4	62.5	
	VO order	611	1.9	5.1	33.6	37.5	non-sign.	

It turned out that formulaicity only had a statistically significant association with linguistic features that were somehow **perceptually** or **conceptually salient**, i.e., features that had more phonetic (and/or graphic) substance or that involved easily noticeable grammatical rules. Conversely, formulaicity had no statistically significant association with less salient features, i.e., features that were so unsubstantial, invisible, or grammatically non-prominent that the scribes, as L2 learners, had not paid due attention to them. Typical examples of features that scribes had not noticed are short morphological endings and syntactic rules like word order issues (on human memory, see section 2.1.). In fact, modern studies on L2 acquisition show that language learners, let alone people in general, tend to be unaware of syntax, while they may have learnt well the vocabulary and inflectional endings of the target language. Medieval Latin teaching also did not pay much attention to syntactic issues.

Early medieval scribes knew they were supposed to use the venerable legal Latin variety, especially in the formulae, which guaranteed the legal validity of the document. In Korciakangas (2018), I suggested that, during and after the original memorization process, the learners who were to become scribes recognized the perceptually and conceptually salient **conservative** features more readily as prestigious Classical Latin forms than the less salient ones and remembered to reproduce those more often in formulaic parts, to which they paid the most attention. On the other hand, the salient **innovative** features, which were felt to belong to the spoken language, were recognized as stigmatized, i.e.,

having a negative prestige, and consequently avoided in the formulaic parts. Non-salient features, instead, whether conservative or innovative, went unnoticed by the scribes and failed to be attributed a (positive or negative) prestige.

2.3. L1 transfer and formulaicity in diachrony

The association between L1 transfer and formulaicity observed in the previous section makes sense, but reality turns out to be more complex once the association is examined in diachrony. The linguistic features examined above are known to have been subject to change between Classical and late Latin or early Romance. However, little is known of the actual progress of this change. It is typical of linguistic change that both the conservative and innovative variants co-occur for a long time, and the progress is only detectable as their slowly reversing proportions. The more formal a written text is, the more complicated is the coexistence of the recessive conservative and emergent innovative features in it. Charter formulae are a blatant manifestation that the conventions shared by the writing community sustain conservative variants. At the same time, the varying paces of change make it difficult to trace the role that formulaicity plays in the distributions of specific linguistic features.

In what follows, I present four diachronic distributions and discuss what they tell us about the underlying linguistic change. Figure 8 presents the distribution of a typical salient linguistic feature. As suggested above, salient innovative variants were felt to belong to the spoken language and avoided in the formulaic parts. Therefore, they occurred less often in the formulaic parts, where the conservative variant held on. As the change proceeded over time, more and more conservative variants were replaced by the innovative variant, which results in the slowly falling trend visible in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Chronology of a typical salient linguistic feature.

Figure 9 shows the diachronic distribution of a typical non-salient feature. The difference between formulaic and free parts is small, irregular, and statistically non-significant on synchronic level. In this case, the diachronic change is also minimal, but note that it can be small or large.

Figure 9. Chronology of a typical non-salient linguistic feature.

The change underlying the distributions in Figures 8 and 9 seems to be relatively linear under the time span examined. However, certain features involve non-linear diachronic paths because of various, partly conflicting tendencies, some of which derive from the actual change of the spoken language, others from extra-linguistic reasons.

The graphs of Figure 10 are about the chronology of a non-salient morphological ending that belonged exclusively to the Subject function in Classical Latin. However, the morpho-syntactic alignment of Latin underwent profound and multi-stage changes from late Latin to early Romance, finally arriving at the loss of morphological distinctions between Subject and Object. In the meantime, the ending was partly replaced by another ending in the Subject function, but the ending also came to be used incorrectly in the Object function by

some scribes. Contrary to the features in Figures 8 and 9, one cannot be sure which variant was conservative and which one innovative at a given time.

Figure 10. Chronology of a non-salient linguistic feature with extra-linguistic interference.

The association of the ending with formulaic/free dichotomy is statistically non-significant in synchrony, as could have been expected. However, in diachrony, an interesting pattern emerges. While the trend lines of the spoken-language-inspired free parts only show a minimal diachronic change, the formulaic parts testify to a relatively steady increase of the ending in the Subject function (correct) and a decrease in the Object function (incorrect).

The improving trends in the formulaic parts cannot be explained by the scribes' improving grammatical skills because that would be visible in the free parts as well. The explanation may be a new document type, *libellus*, which spread rapidly in Tuscia from the beginning of the 9th century and which seems to have been introduced by the new Frankish rulers following the conquest of Italy in 774 (Korkiakangas 2023b). This new document type was probably drafted in Francia. Unlike Tuscan spoken Latin, the Old French morphosyntactic system maintained a clearer opposition between the morphological endings of Subjects and Objects. Thus, the improving correct trends (see especially the sudden drop of the incorrect Object ending at around 800) might result from a change in the formula use.

The free parts, instead, were immune to changing documentary practices and went on reflecting the situation of the spoken language with a heavily reduced morphosyntactic system, where the generalization of the ending to all syntactic functions was well advanced. The scribes' grammatical knowledge was still enough to make them avoid it in ca. 70% of Objects, whereas its high number in Subjects undoubtedly derives from its real

distribution in the spoken language. This explanation supports the view, suggested above in passing, that formulae really were sometimes copied using physical models – which is likely to have become more usual by the standardization of charter production in the 9th century.

3. Conclusions

Formulaicity must be taken into account when early medieval charters are used for (corpus-)linguistic analysis. Distributional comparisons to other corpora should be made carefully due to the over-/under-representation of linguistic features present/absent in the formulae. The psycholinguistic concept of perceptual and conceptual saliency is useful in finding out which features can be taken to reflect the contemporary spoken language rather than the age-old legal Latin. Even the formulaic passages can serve diachronic linguistics as long as the focus is on non-salient features, which typically escaped the scribes' notice. Broadly speaking, non-salient features, such as many syntactic constructions and short morphological inflections, can be more reliably studied corpus-linguistically without paying attention to formulaicity, while salient features should be examined separately in formulaic and free parts. However, although the formulae of private charters were usually reproduced from memory, physical models seem to have been used increasingly in the 9th century. This even appears to be visible in the diachronic distributions of some non-salient features. Thus, trends in documentary production, administrative changes, and educational practices should all be considered alongside formulaicity, when analysing the diachronic distributions of linguistic features of charters.

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